

Introduction to Engineering Design

Research Methods
(Week 6)

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Outline

- Introduction
- Research Methods

Learning Objectives to be achieved:

1. To identify the research methods
2. To get the skills in creating the research methods to be used in the design process.

Introduction

- This sixth-week topic aims to help the engineering designer to grasp the ability to search for information and use it to identify the gaps and create a new idea.
- The fifth-week topics correspond to the fourth-course objectives, which state, "Develop a conceptual design with the material specification based on broad design parameters including cost and sustainability".

Introduction (2)

- The fourth week's topics respond to the first-course objective, "To identify and apply the various phases and processes within an engineering design process".
- The third week's topics discuss communication, collaboration and team success, even in a diverse team membership or multi-disciplinary nature.

Introduction (3)

- The second week's response to the second-course objective states, "On completion of this subject, the students can participate within and contribute to a multi-discipline engineering design team through the application of team roles and communication".
- In the first week's discussion, the challenge to take part in the Sustainable Development Goals action using the Greening Engineering Framework (GEF) that served as a theme to the Engineering Design Challenge 2022, was taken on board as an engineering design team is discussed and organised in the second week.

3.1 The Research Method

3.1.1 The purpose of a research study (Conceptualization Phase)

- ✓ describe the prevalence of a specific condition within a targeted population,
- ✓ investigate the relationship between two variables,
- ✓ establish whether (i.e., how and to what degree) a particular intervention or program is beneficial, or
- ✓ understand which factors (i.e., independent variables) influence a specific dependent variable (e.g., behaviour, condition, or outcome).
- ✓ The purpose of research is to gather information.

The Research Method

3.2 Skills in creating research methods

3.2.1 Quantitative Methods

- Much of engineering research seeks to identify how outcomes (i.e., mechanical failure) are determined by reducing plausible causes to a discrete set of indicators or variables. Quantitative methods are a good fit for deductive approaches, in which a theory or hypothesis justifies the variables, the purpose statement, and the direction of the narrowly defined research questions. (Maura Borrego)

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3.2 Skills in creating research methods

The purpose of quantitative studies is for the researcher to project his or her findings onto the larger population through an objective process. (Maura Borrego)

The goals of quantitative studies, include:

- ✓ causal determination,
- ✓ prediction, and
- ✓ generalisation of findings

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3.2 Skills in creating research methods

- In quantitative studies, sample size goals are large numbers. However, in qualitative studies, participant numbers are generally small, so the population can be explored in depth (Daly, McGowan, & Papalambros)
- Rigour is represented by the terms reliability and validity in quantitative research (Daly, McGowan, & Papalambros)

3.2 Skills in creating research methods

3.2.2 Qualitative Methods

- Qualitative research is characterised by the collection and analysis of textual data (surveys, interviews, focus groups, conversational, investigation, observation, and ethnographies). The research questions that qualitative studies can answer are questions such as: What is occurring? Why does something happen? How does one phenomenon affect another? While numbers can be used to summarise qualitative data, answering these questions generally requires detailed, contextual descriptions of the data, often called a "thick" description. (Maura Borrego)

3.2 Skills in creating research methods

3.2.2 Qualitative Methods

The goals of qualitative research are:

- ✓ illumination,
- ✓ understanding,
- ✓ and extrapolation of findings to similar situations

3.2 Skills in creating research methods

3.2.2 Qualitative Methods

Qualitative investigations do not attempt to control for the context but instead seek to describe it in-depth so as to incorporate the context into deriving and explaining research findings (Daly, McGowan, & Papalambros)

Key questions in Qualitative Research (Daly, McGowan, & Papalambros)

- ✓ What is occurring?
- ✓ How is something occurring?
- ✓ Why is something occurring? What impacts the occurrence of a phenomenon?

3.2 Skills in creating research methods

3.2.2 Qualitative Methods

Methods of Qualitative Research (Daly, McGowan, & Papalambros)

- ✓ Driven by the goal of detail, methods like interviews and observations are dominant in qualitative.
- ✓ other textual forms of data, such as open-ended surveys, dialogues, focus groups, and documents
- ✓ A repeatable procedure with unbiased questions grounded in literature should be made to demonstrate validity and reliability.

3.2 Skills in creating research methods

3.2.2 Qualitative Methods

Data analysis in qualitative research can be:
(Daly, McGowan, & Papalambros)

- ✓ *Inductive.* Inductive analysis refers to developing themes emergently based on patterns in the data
- ✓ *Deductive.* Deductive analysis refers to determining a coding scheme before looking at the data
- ✓ or a combination of **both**.

3.2 Skills in creating research methods

3.2.2 Qualitative Methods

- Qualitative research appropriately done is as rigorous as positivist approaches to quantitative studies (Daly, McGowan, & Papalambros)
- Qualitative research uses terms such as trustworthiness and transferability. Trustworthiness means that the researcher collects and systematically analyses the data and presents the data and the synthesis and interpretation of data transparently to others. (Daly, McGowan, & Papalambros)

3.2 Skills in creating research methods

3.2.2 Qualitative Methods

- Research papers written on qualitative studies are often longer than quantitative study reports. In addition to detailed description and transparency, triangulation, meaning.
- Transferability refers to the extent to which research findings can apply to contexts other than the study context from which the conclusions emerged that; describe transferability as having enough thick description of a specific context that will allow readers of the research to make connections to

3.2 Skills in creating research methods

3.2.2 Qualitative Methods

Drawbacks:

- ✓ Individual skills of the researcher and subject to biases of the researcher.
- ✓ qualitative findings are not often generalisable.

3.2 Skills in creating research methods

3.2.2 Qualitative Methods

- Qualitative findings can serve as a foundation for quantitative studies or qualitative studies can help explore the how and why questions emerging from a quantitative research.
- Using these existing examples of qualitative research in engineering design and foundational resources on qualitative methods to guide our work, we developed a study to investigate interdisciplinary interactions during the research, development, and early conceptual design phases of large-scale complex engineered systems. (Daly, McGowan, & Papalambros)

3.2 Skills in creating research methods

3.2.3 Mixed method

- A mixed methods study involves the collection or analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data in a single study in which the data are collected concurrently or sequentially, are given a priority and involve the integration of the data at one or more stages in the process of research. (Maura Borrego)
- Mixed-methods approaches, combining qualitative and quantitative methods, are sometimes used to investigate a research goal with multiple perspectives, taking advantage of the strengths of qualitative and quantitative methods.

3.3 The Process of Research in Engineering Design

Design research can be considered to have passed through three overlapping phases:

(Daly, McGowan, & Papalambros)

- ✓ experiential,
- ✓ intellectual and
- ✓ experimental

3.3 The Process of Research in Engineering Design

Design research methodology –
types of design research: (Daly,
McGowan, & Papalambros)

- ✓ focusing,
- ✓ planning and
- ✓ executing design research.

3.3 The Process of Research in Engineering Design

Figure 21 Design research methodology

3.3 The Process of Research in Engineering Design

Figure 21 above shows the Methodology framework of design research which consists of basic methods, results and focus. Design research is about developing strategies and tools for improving the design.

Figure 21 Design research methodology framework (Chakrabarti)

3.3 The Process of Research in Engineering Design

Figure 21 Design research methodology framework (Chakrabarti)

Descriptive Study I. Involves studying design to increase our understanding directly or through reasoning based on a literature review. The focus can be on the product (e.g. product reliability) as well as on the process of designing (e.g. setting up requirements lists)

3.3 The Process of Research in Engineering Design

Prescriptive Study. Literature is used to obtain an understanding of the various factors that influence, directly or indirectly, the measurable criterion.

Figure 21 Design research methodology framework (Chakrabarti)

3.3 The Process of Research in Engineering Design

Descriptive Study II. It is undertaken to evaluate the application of the method developed in the prescriptive study. It includes two tests. The application evaluation assesses the functionality from a user point of view, that is: can the support be applied; does it indeed address those factors it is supposed to address directly; are these factors affected as expected?

Figure 21 Design research methodology framework (Chakrabarti)

3.3 The Process of Research in Engineering Design

Figure 21 Design research methodology framework (Chakrabarti)

CRITERIA FORMULATION	DESCRIPTIVE STUDY I	PRESCRIPTIVE STUDY	DESCRIPTIVE STUDY II
Review	Detailed		
Review	Detailed	Initial	
Review	Review	Detailed	Initial
Review	Review	Review	Detailed
		Initial/ Detailed	
Review	Detailed	Detailed	Initial
Review	Review	Detailed	Detailed
Review	Detailed	Detailed	Detailed

Arrows in the table indicate the flow of information and feedback between stages. Horizontal arrows point from left to right between adjacent stages. Vertical arrows point from the bottom row up to the top row in each column. Dashed lines with arrows indicate feedback loops from 'Detailed' stages back to 'Review' stages in the same column.

References

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“RESEARCH
IS THE **PROCESS**
OF GOING
UP ALLEYS
TO SEE IF THEY
ARE BLIND.”

Marston Bates

Thank you